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The Impact of COVID-19 on Work, Exit, and Exclusion Among Older Workers

Authors: Andreea Alecu, Arianna Vivoli, Maria Johanna Aartsen,
Iuliana Precupetu, Elisabeth Ugreninov

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PATHS2INCLUDE

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European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations

Title: The Impact of COVID-19 on Work, Exit, and Exclusion Among Older Workers

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Author(s): Andreea Alecu, Arianna Vivoli, Maria Johanna Aartsen, Iuliana Precupetu, Elisabeth Ugreninov

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Introduction

This working paper is part of PATHS2INCLUDE, a research project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe (101094626). The overall objective of PATHS2INCLUDE is to disentangle the dimensions of discrimination and unequal opportunities in the labour market to gain knowledge on how to develop inclusive labour markets for persons in vulnerable situations. A key goal is to understand how contextual factors disproportionately expose certain groups to risk and vulnerability throughout their life course and during critical transitions. The working paper is part of Work Package 5, with the overarching goal to study employment policies and institutional and individual factors affecting employment among older workers.

In this working paper we address the broader issue of older individuals' participation in the labour market in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. The focus is twofold: on the one hand, it examines employment trends, and the dynamics of both voluntary and involuntary labour market exits among older workers during the pandemic period, with particular attention to how the crisis influenced retirement and withdrawal decisions. On the other hand, it investigates a different but closely related phenomenon: the risk of labour market exclusion due to prolonged inactivity among older individuals who are not formally retired but are no longer engaged in employment. This situation may reflect hidden forms of marginalisation, especially in contexts where reintegration into the workforce becomes increasingly difficult with age.

The ageing of societies has put the sustainability of pension systems under pressure, and many governments have introduced pension reforms to alleviate this pressure, of which one is the increased mandatory retirement age, and the other is the introduction of labour market reforms to support older workers to keep them active in the labour market. In the decision to exit the labour market towards retirement, it is generally assumed that people weight the benefits and costs of extending working life against the benefits and costs of an early exit (Hofäcker et al., 2016). Two factors that may be decisive in this evaluation are education and gender. People with higher education often have jobs with higher income, lower health risks, higher satisfaction with life and better access to information concerning retirement planning and benefits than people with lower levels of education. Compared to men, women more often have, and are more often expected to have, care responsibilities which makes it harder to balance work and family responsibilities. At the same time, the career-breaks and more often part-time jobs lead to lower pensions which in fact can be a reason to prolong working life as women cannot afford to stop early (Finch, 2014). Several empirical studies indicated that the social gradient is most visible in involuntary labour-market exit. For example, in Europe, lower educated workers are more likely to involuntarily exit the labour market, while there was no educational difference in voluntary exit (Mäcken et al., 2022). This educational gradient in involuntary labour-market exit was particularly strong for women in a study among Norwegian people (Dahl, Nilsen & Vaage, 2003). Gender differences in labour-market exit are also observed for reasons to retire, but retirement trajectories were not largely different for men and women, at least in Finland (Riekhoff & Järnefelt, 2017).

These same factors, education, gender, and unpaid care responsibilities, also represent key determinants of labour market inactivity among older individuals who are not yet retired. Lower-educated individuals are more likely to face significant barriers to re-entering the labour market, often due to health issues, skills mismatches, or limited access to reskilling opportunities. Similarly, women with intermittent career trajectories and substantial care burdens may be

pushed into inactivity, particularly in the absence of supportive policies such as flexible working arrangements or eldercare services (Humphrey et al., 2003; Dantas et al., 2017).

The outbreak of COVID-19 significantly impacted daily life across Europe. Disease control measures, including restrictions on social distancing and workplace presence, along with high unemployment rates, disproportionately affected at-risk groups' ability to remain attached to the labour market (OECD, 2021). Although the recovery was swifter compared to e.g. the Great Recession, the post-pandemic labour market may present challenges for older workers in several ways.

First, the COVID-19 pandemic posed economic downturn and an increase in the workforce departure (European Central Bank, 2022). Second, older adults were at greater risk of severe illness and mortality from COVID-19 additionally to reduced access to healthcare for non-COVID-related conditions (Graves, 2020; Masroor, 2020; Oyebode, Ramsay & Brayne, 2021; Raifman, Bor & Venkataramani, 2020; Jiskrova et al., 2021). Third, during the COVID-19 pandemic, governments mandated widespread remote work (Ker, Montagnier & Spiezia, 2021) that may have posed challenges in older workers due to lower digital proficiency and reduced workplace social interaction, potentially influencing retirement decisions (Hauk et al., 2018; Carstensen & Reynolds, 2023; Schellaert & Derous, 2023).

The working paper is organised as follows, first a short overview of the impact of COVID-19 on older workers, then divided into two main parts: Section A explores the dynamics of both voluntary and involuntary exits from the labour market among older workers during the COVID-19 pandemic, drawing on data from the SHARE survey. Section B uses data from the EU-SILC to examine the risk of labour market exclusion among older individuals who are no longer employed but have not formally remarks retired, focusing on cases of prolonged inactivity that may signal marginalisation rather than a deliberate retirement decision. Both sections describe the data sources, methodological approach, the main findings, and concluding remarks.

The COVID-19 pandemic and work exit among older workers

The COVID-19 pandemic posed economic downturns and an increase in the workforce departure. The sharp drop in older workers' labour force participation in Europe and in the U.S. (Hout et al., 2020) represents a clear break in an otherwise steady increase over the past 20 years (European Central Bank, 2022). Older workers who were furloughed or displaced during the pandemic faced difficulties in securing new employment opportunities. Some opted for early retirement, either due to health concerns or a lack of viable job options, leading to an overall decline in labour force participation among older age groups (OECD, 2021). In contrast to the Great Recession, Europe and the U.S. experienced a relatively swift return to pre-pandemic participation rate, though the increase is not at the same expected level observed in previous years (Chen and Munnell, 2021; Domash & Summers, 2022; European Central Bank, 2022; Munnell & Chen, 2021). In the aftermath of the Great Recession, older workers experienced difficulties to re-enter the labour market due to high unemployment (Coe & Haverstick, 2010; Goda et al., 2011; Helman et al., 2011) and poor prospects of suitable jobs (Munnell & Rutledge, 2013).

A significant portion of the relevant literature examining the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on employment, workforce departure, and retirement is from the U.S., which may not

accurately reflect the post-pandemic situation in Europe. However, we consider it useful to include this research. Recent U.S. studies utilising the monthly Current Population Survey (CPS) identified significant age-related differences among older workers. While workers aged 55-64 were not disproportionately affected compared to younger age groups (Munnell & Chen, 2021; Sanzenbacher, 2021), the opposite was observed among workers aged 65 and above (Bui et al., 2020; Jacobson et al., 2020; Coile & Zhang, 2022). Reasons for leaving the labour market differ, with the discrepancy between leaving work (e.g., inactivity, unemployment) and retirement being larger pre-pandemic than post-pandemic (Davis et al., 2023). A study by Goda and colleagues (2022) indicated that some workers below the age of 70 left their jobs but did not retire, subsequently re-entering employment. Other studies found a different pattern among the oldest workers post-pandemic. A steady increase in retirement through 2022 may be due to the greater difficulties they experienced in re-entering the workforce, or because they already had plans for imminent retirement and used other sources of income in the meantime (Forsythe et al., 2022; Montes, Smith & Dajon, 2022).

The COVID-19 pandemic introduced an additional health risk that disproportionately affected older adults. Generally, older adults faced a higher risk of severe illness and mortality from COVID-19 (Bauer et al., 2021; Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021; Jordan et al., 2020). Additionally, healthcare utilisation for non-COVID-19 related conditions was reduced (Masroor, 2020; Oyebode et al., 2021; Raifman et al., 2020), which may have compromised their overall health status (Jiskrova et al., 2021). Recent research indicates that psychological challenges and mental states correlate significantly with various demographic characteristics of employees, such as age, income, parental status, job type, gender, and education level (Dinibutun, 2020; Kuo et al., 2020; Park et al., 2020; Teng et al., 2020). Furthermore, older workers are more likely to face different job demands and eldercare responsibilities compared to their younger counterparts (Blount, 2019). These factors may contribute to differential health and well-being outcomes between older and younger workers during the COVID-19 pandemic. Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, many older workers faced heightened health risks and disproportionate job loss, leading to an increase in early retirement during the first-year post pandemic in the U.S labour market (Davis, 2021, Davis et. al., 2023). Consequently, the aging workforce may struggle to cope with increased employment uncertainty and job demands, potentially affecting their retirement timing intentions.

During the COVID-19 crisis, extensive use of remote work, primarily from home, was mandated by the governments (Ker, Montagnier & Spiezia, 2021). A clear distinction exists between voluntary and non-voluntary remote working. A study by Kazekami (2020) shows that voluntarily remote work, before the COVID-19 pandemic, had several positive benefits and increased productivity. During the COVID-19 non-voluntary remote work was widespread, which among other factors, negatively impacted many workers satisfaction and performance (Camacho & Barrios, 2022). Recent research indicates that older workers' perceptions of remote work during the COVID-19 were more negative compared to their younger adult counterparts (Raisiene et al., 2020). The increased reliance on digital technology in the workplace imposed additional demands on older workers (Anderson & Kelliher, 2020; Gigauri, 2020; Morrow-Howell, Galucia, & Swinford, 2020). Furthermore, among older workers with higher health risks (Bauer et al., 2021), caregiving responsibilities (Cui et al., 2023), and lower technology acceptance or knowledge (Hauk et al., 2018), remote work made a potential source of strain. The advantages and disadvantages of remote work are described in a nuanced manner in the review articles by Beckel and Fisher (2022) and Mun et al. (2022).

Remote work naturally leads to less or limited contact with colleagues. For older adults, the absence of the social aspect of being at work and the forced technology learning, often without

adequate support and resources, may have influenced decisions regarding retirement behaviour. According to the socioemotional selectivity theory, as people age, they become more inclined to focus on emotionally meaningful experiences rather than on learning and exploration activities (Carstensen & Reynolds, 2023). This shift in priorities may further influence older workers' retirement decisions, as they might opt for retirement over adapting to new work environments that lack social interaction and require significant technological adjustments (Schellaert & Deros, 2023). Thus, forced remote work and technology adoption may pose significant challenges and additional demands in older workers (Anderson & Kelliher, 2020; Gigauri, 2020; Morrow-Howell, Galucia, & Swinford, 2020).

Part A - Investigating voluntary and involuntary exit of older people: a cross-country analysis using SHARE data.

Introduction

In the decision to exit the labour market, it is generally assumed that people weigh the benefits and costs of extending working life against the benefits and costs of an early exit (Hofäcker et al., 2016). Despite this apparently rational process, the outcomes of decisions to exit the labour market are often socially patterned. This study investigates inequalities in labour-market exit, and how these may have changed during the COVID-19 pandemic. Factors typically associated with the social patterning of labour market exit are education and gender. People with higher education often have jobs with higher income, lower health risks, higher satisfaction and better access to information concerning retirement planning and benefits which may affect the timing of retirement.

In our study, we further differentiate between voluntary and involuntary exit as two qualitative different types of labour-market exit. Voluntary exit is typically associated with the preference for leisure relative to work, whereas involuntary exit is related to employment constraints (Dorn & Sousa-Poza, 2008). Voluntary and involuntary exits tend to be socially patterned as well, with lower educated workers more likely to exit the labour market involuntarily than higher educated people (Mäcken et al., 2022). We also include health in our analytical model as low self-perceived health is a major determinant of labour market exit, either because it limits the ability to work, or because it leads to the eligibility of disability benefit programs that provides alternative sources for income (Avendano & Mackenbach, 2011).

In addition, we evaluate several factors that can potentially be linked to voluntary or involuntary work exits. The first is loneliness. Loneliness arises when the actual quality or quantity of social relations is lower than desired (Perlman and Peplau, 1980). Enhancing the quality or quantity of the relations one has can mitigate feelings of loneliness. By providing additional free time, retirement can offer new opportunities to renew and improve social connections, potentially reducing loneliness (Guthmuller et al., 2024). However, individuals who have heavily invested in their careers may have underdeveloped social networks outside of work. For these individuals,

retirement might result in incomplete social networks, social isolation, and increased feelings of loneliness. Next, we include a variable that is indicative of the time spent on caring for others in the family and beyond. A task that is typically linked to women. Women more often have care responsibilities which may induce career-brakes and part-time jobs leading to lower pensions which in fact can be a reason to prolong working life if women cannot afford to stop early (Finch, 2014). Finally, we consider the role of having a partner on the decision for a voluntary or involuntary work exit. People with a partner are often wealthier than singles (Gallagher & Waite, 2000), and therefore less affected by a potential drop in income after retirement. This may impact the decision to voluntarily exit the labour market. But there may be also differences in non-financial arguments between partnered and single workers, as is shown in a previous study using SHARE data. It was concluded that the social network, among which the partner, is a key factor in the timing of retirement (Litwin et al., 2015). People whose partner is already retired are more likely to retire early than those whose partner is still working.

This study provides answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the pattern in voluntary and involuntary labour-market exit and did this change during the pandemic?
2. Are age, education, helping others, loneliness, self-perceived health and having a partner in the household associated with an increased risk of voluntary work exit?
3. Are age, education, helping others, loneliness, self-perceived health and having a partner in the household associated with an increased risk of involuntary work exit?

Because of the intersectionality of the predictor variables with gender, all models are estimated separately for men and women.

Data and sample

Our analysis relies on data derived from the Survey of Health and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) study (Börsch-Supan et al., 2013). SHARE is a longitudinal survey including persons with the age of 50 years or more who live regularly in their country, are not incarcerated, hospitalised or out of the country during the survey. Spouses or partners are also included in the target population even if they are younger than 50 years. Our primary interests are to study work exit before and after the COVID-19 pandemic, following the same persons. As such, the study sample consisted of all persons 50 years and above who were employed during Wave 7 (2017), who were interviewed at Wave 8 (2019), and at Wave 9 (2023) (Wave 8 and Wave 9 (release versions: 9.0.0)). Although the data collection of Wave 8 was not completed when the COVID-19 pandemic started, we used this wave because of the more complete information on the job characteristics and other related variables as compared to Wave 7. *Table 1* gives an overview of the number of respondents in our analytical sample after the countries included in SHARE.

Table 1 Number of respondents in Wave 8 and Wave 9 after country

Country	Wave 8 (N)	Wave 9 (N)
Austria	184	153
Germany	797	646
Sweden	463	400
Spain	287	111
Italy	416	382
France	418	345
Denmark	749	604
Greece	369	316
Switzerland	528	420
Belgium	408	359
Israel	207	94
Czech Republic	323	251
Poland	444	376
Luxembourg	150	116
Hungary	99	81
Slovenia	268	252
Estonia	862	760
Croatia	186	173
Lithuania	417	381
Bulgaria	204	157
Cyprus	71	50
Finland	331	231
Latvia	201	188
Malta	137	115
Romania	175	154
Slovakia	415	387
Total	9109	7502

Methodology

Dependent variable

We aim to describe voluntary and involuntary exit from the labour market by using a dependent variable with three categories; 1) continued labour-market participation, currently employed, since the last observation (reference category), 2) voluntary exit, and 3) involuntary exit. Voluntary and involuntary work exit is based on a series of questions about the reasons for retirement. In line with other work (e.g., Mäcken et al., 2022) we counted the following reasons for retirement as indicative for a voluntary work exit: becoming available for public or private pension, was offered an early retirement option/window with special incentives or bonus, to enjoy life, to spend more time with family, retire together with the spouse, and becoming a homemaker. Indicative for involuntary retirement included made redundant (for example pre-

retirement), own or other people’s ill health, becoming permanently sick or disabled, becoming unemployed.

Independent variable

Education reflects the number of years in full-time education. *Self-perceived health* is an ordinary variable with five answering categories ranging from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). *Gender* is coded 1 for male and 2 for female. *Helping others* is measured with the question “How much time did you spend yesterday on helping your children, grandchildren, parents, parents in law, partner, and others on the day before? Answering categories are Did not help (0), Less than 30 minutes (1), Between 30 and 60 minutes (2) and More than 60 minutes (3). *Loneliness* was measured with a direct question “Do you feel lonely”, with answering categories Never or hardly ever (1), Some of the time (2) and Often (3). *Self-perceived health* is assessed with the question “Would you say your health is...” Excellent (1), Very good (2), Good (3), Fair (4) or Poor (5). Finally, we used information about *having a partner in the household*, which was coded as 1 if a partner was in the household, and 0 if there was no partner in the household.

Analytical approach

After the descriptive statistics we conducted two multinomial logistic regression, one for wave 8 (2019) and one for wave 9 (2023). The dependent variable is the nominal variable type of job exit, which includes voluntary exit and involuntary exit, and the reference category is currently employed.

Table 2 Current job situation in Wave 8 and Wave 9 of SHARE of people aged 50+ who were employed at SHARE Wave 7

	Current job situation Wave 8 (2019)			Current job situation Wave 9 (2023)		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Retired	2199	24.1	24.2	3141	34.5	42.4
(Self-)employed	6307	69.2	69.4	3742	41.1	50.5
Unemployed	243	2.7	2.7	141	1.5	1.9
Permanently sick or disabled	138	1.5	1.5	152	1.7	2.1
Homemaker	97	1.1	1.1	115	1.3	1.6
Other	108	1.2	1.2	113	1.2	1.5
Missing information	17	0.2		98	1.1	
Total	9109	100		7502	100	

In 2023, of the 6307 people still employed in 2019, 1475 (26,2%) had voluntarily left the labour market in 2023 and 404 (7.2%) involuntarily (*Table 2*). Labour-market exit is in most cases voluntary, both before the pandemic (Wave 8) as after (Wave 9). By far, the most important reason for a voluntary work exit is becoming eligible for pension. Other reasons, such as more time for leisure activities or retiring with one’s partner is rarely reported, and this has not changed much after the pandemic.

Table 3 Reasons for retirement at Wave 8 and Wave 9 for people 50 years and above who were employed at Wave 7

Wave 8					
Voluntary work exit	N	%	Involuntary work exit	N	%
Still employed	6415	70.4	Still employed	6415	70.4
Became eligible for pension	1529	16.8	Disability retirement	225	2.5
Was offered early retirement	103	1.2	Unemployed	281	3.1
To enjoy life	151	1.7	Retired due to other people's health	13	0.1
To spend more time with family	87	1.0			
Retire with spouse	43	0.5			
Became homemaker	97	1.1			
Involuntary work exit	294	6.1	Voluntary work exit	2010	21.7
Missing information	390	7.3	Missing information	165	1.8
Total	9109			9109	

Wave 9					
Voluntary work exit	N	%	Involuntary work exit	N	%
Still employed	3610	57.2	Still employed	3610	57.2
Became eligible for pension	986	15.6	Disability retirement	128	2.0
Was offered early retirement	52	0.8	Unemployed	113	1.8
To enjoy life	84	1.3	Retired due to other people's health	9	0.1
To spend more time with family	61	1.0			
Retire with spouse	19	0.3			
Became homemaker	48	0.8			
Involuntary work exit	122	1.9	Voluntary work exit	1250	19.8
Missing information	1325	21.0	Missing information	1197	19.9
	6307			6307	

Multinomial logistic regression (MLR) are used for answering research questions 2 and 3, focusing on the social pattern of labour-market exit. Research questions 2 and 3 focused on the social pattern of labour-market exit. By means of two MLR-analyses (one for the 2019 data and one for the 2023 data), we evaluated whether the likelihood for a voluntary or involuntary exit as compared to currently employed was altered by helping others, feelings of loneliness, self-perceived health, and having a partner in the household, while taking into account age and education. Both models were estimated separately for men and women. The results of the MLR analyses are in [Table A3](#) (2023, men) and [Table A4](#) (2023, women).

The results show that a voluntary exit of the labour-market is more likely when people are older (unstandardized b's range from 0.21 to 0.25), as compared to those who continue working. This association remains unchanged after the pandemic and is comparable for men and women. Involuntary exit is not associated with age for men and women before the pandemic. On the other hand, after the pandemic, women were more likely to experience an involuntary exit when they were older. For men, age was unrelated to involuntary exit. Lower levels of education are consistently associated with higher likelihood of exiting the labour market, both voluntary and

involuntary, across both time periods and for both men and women (b's range from -0.04 to -0.07).

Furthermore, helping others substantially increases the risk for a voluntary and involuntary exit of the labour market for men, both before and after the pandemic (b's for providing less than one hour help per day range from -0.24 to -0.64). For women a similar pattern was observed, except for involuntary exit, which was not affected by helping others before the pandemic. Loneliness is unrelated to a voluntary labour-market exit for men and women. However, loneliness increases the risk of an involuntary exit for both men and women (b's for not being lonely is -0.90 for both men and women) before the pandemic, but this impact lost its significance after the pandemic. Self-rated health has a consistent impact on involuntary labour-market exit for both men and women, and this has not changed after the pandemic. Compared to people who have a poor self-rated health, people with better self-rated health are less likely to make an involuntary exit (b's for better than poor self-rated health range from -0.86 to -3.86). For voluntary exit, the effect is smaller and only reaches borderline significance in men before the pandemic (b for excellent self-rated health is -0.79 , and for fair self-rated health -0.81). Having a partner in the household does not affect the odds of a voluntary or involuntary labour-market exit for men, but women's choice for a voluntary work exit is inflated when there is a partner in the household (b for not having a partner as compared to having a partner in the household is -0.40) and this association remains significant after the pandemic. An involuntary exit is also unrelated to an involuntary exit for women.

Concluding remarks

Our study aimed to provide important insights into the patterns of voluntary and involuntary labour market exit among older workers before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Using longitudinal data from the SHARE survey across multiple European countries, our analysis demonstrates that labour market exit decisions are significantly influenced by sociodemographic characteristics, health status, and social circumstances, with notable gender differences in these patterns. Results reveal both persistent inequalities and emerging vulnerabilities among older workers.

Age consistently emerges as the most significant factor of voluntary labour market exit, with older workers consistently more likely to retire across both time periods and genders. Education is as a key factor in both voluntary and involuntary exits, with lower-educated workers facing higher risks of leaving the labour market regardless of the reason. Poor health status is consistently associated with involuntary labour market exit. Furthermore, our gender-stratified analysis reveals important differences in how personal circumstances affect labour market decisions. For women, having a partner increases the likelihood of voluntary exit, reflecting traditional gender roles and possibly greater financial security - due to partnership - that enables early retirement choices. This clear social patterning of exit underscores the influence of social and relational factors on retirement decisions and the importance of targeted support for extended working lives, particularly as labour markets evolve post-pandemic.

The comparison between pre-pandemic and pandemic periods reveals that while many established patterns persisted, COVID-19 introduced new vulnerabilities, particularly affecting older women's risk of involuntary exit. While loneliness increased the risk of an involuntary exit for both men and women before the pandemic, this impact was significantly diminished after the pandemic. As COVID-19 heightened social isolation and loneliness across populations, it likely reduced the variation in loneliness levels among older workers. As loneliness became more

widespread, its differential influence on employment status have diminished, making it a less distinctive factor in exit decisions. Furthermore, policy responses during the pandemic—such as extended unemployment benefits, temporary retirement age adjustments, and increased social support—possibly buffered some of the adverse effects associated with social and health vulnerabilities, thereby reducing the direct impact of loneliness on involuntary exits.

Caregiving responsibilities increase labour market exit risks, revealing important gender differences pre-and post-pandemic. For men, providing care consistently increased both voluntary and involuntary exit risks before and during the pandemic, a pattern exposing the difficulties encountered by men in a realm traditionally assumed by women. Results suggest that men, unlike women, have fewer established networks, resources, or workplace policies designed to help balance care and work responsibilities, while generally caregiving is less normalized for them. For women, before COVID-19, caregiving responsibilities increased voluntary exit risk but not involuntary exit risk, whereas post-pandemic involuntary exit risk increased. This pattern is likely due to established workplace accommodations, legal protections, and social norms. Women also had over time developed effective strategies—such as flexible work arrangements and shared care—to manage responsibilities, which probably helped prevent job loss. Caregiving was socially expected and professionally accommodated, providing a buffer against involuntary employment exit. Post-pandemic increase of women's involuntary job exits was likely due to intensified care demands that overwhelmed existing coping strategies. Support systems were largely affected, with reduced or unavailable family, paid and community care, while health restrictions made informal care sharing impossible. Workplace dynamics also shifted as remote work blurred boundaries, employers became less tolerant of caregiving impacts amid economic pressures and general heightened job insecurity. Coupled with financial stress and gendered assumptions, these factors possibly led to more "acceptable" layoffs of women with family responsibilities during the pandemic.

To conclude, our study demonstrates that labour market exit is not simply an individual choice but is shaped by personal circumstances, social structures, and external shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic. This event has both highlighted existing vulnerabilities and created new challenges, emphasizing the need for adaptive and inclusive policy responses that support older workers in making the transition out of the labour market.

PART B - Older workers and the risk of labour market exclusion: a cross-country analysis using EU-SILC data

Introduction

This part of the working paper focuses on a specific dynamic affecting older individuals: the risk of exclusion from the labour market. Unlike studies that investigate the nuances of retirement decisions, often supported by dedicated survey instruments such as the SHARE dataset used in previous sections, our research concentrates specifically on the contextual and individual factors leading to labour market exclusion among the elderly. Importantly, this is a distinct concept from retirement: in our analysis, individuals who report being retired are included in the "not-at-risk" group, as retirement represents a legitimate, institutionalised, and socially accepted pathway out of the labour market. It does not necessarily imply marginalisation or involuntary withdrawal.

Labour market exclusion refers to the processes by which older workers are pushed out of or marginalised from employment, either voluntarily or involuntarily, before reaching the statutory retirement age. This exclusion can take different forms, but in our operationalisation, it is identified by a prolonged period of inactivity. This is precisely the focus of our study. We restrict our sample to respondents aged 50 to 70, targeting those who are approaching retirement age or who may have already exited the labour market but remain potentially employable. As such, they are at risk of social and economic marginalisation, particularly in contexts where reintegration into the workforce is difficult.

Drawing on the cross-sectional component of the EU-SILC dataset (2010–2022), we adopt a multilevel modelling approach to examine both individual-level and regional/national-level determinants of this risk. We specifically explore the condition of older individuals in general, and by comparing the pre-pandemic and immediate post-pandemic periods. To better understand the role of policy context, we also investigate the potential influence of national-level COVID-19 containment measures, by incorporating country-level data from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). This enables us to exploit cross-national variation in how different governments responded to the crisis.

These analyses are particularly relevant in the post-COVID context, as older workers were among the most affected groups, both directly, due to the greater health risks associated with the virus, and indirectly, in terms of employment outcomes. While some have discussed the "retirement surge" following the pandemic, in Europe this phenomenon was less pronounced than in contexts like the U.S. (Botelho and Weessler, 2022). Instead, a key concern in the European case has been the increase in inactivity among older individuals during the pandemic: many people nearing retirement age lost their jobs or closed their businesses and subsequently stopped looking for new employment, effectively anticipating their withdrawal from the labour market.

This early exit is driven by multiple factors: health-related risks, the nature of one's occupation, and the strength of social protection systems. From a health perspective, COVID-19 posed a particularly severe threat to older individuals. Senior workers in essential roles were often

forced to choose between income security and exposure to infection; many opted for early withdrawal due to fear of severe illness. Simultaneously, older workers were overrepresented in occupations that could not be performed remotely, which left them especially vulnerable. They faced not only higher health risks, but also job loss when physical workplaces were shut down. In contrast, older individuals in white-collar or managerial positions were more likely to transition to remote work, preserving both their employment and health. This divide has widened pre-existing inequalities: for instance, low-income or manual workers experienced far more pronounced increases in inactivity compared to their more educated or highly qualified peers during 2020–2021 (Hecker et al., 2021).

In this study we are employing a set of multi-level analyses covering the 2010 to 2022 period to better understand what may influence elderly workers' (50 years age or above) to exit the labour market. The models account for regional variation at the NUTS1 or NUTS2 level, depending on data availability. This allows us to better gauge the importance of both personal characteristics and contextual dynamics. Our findings largely align with the existing literature. The risk of labour market exclusion in later life disproportionately affects the most vulnerable groups: individuals with low levels of education, women, and those with health-related limitations. What is particularly noteworthy is how membership in higher social classes, proxied here by wealth quintiles, buffers against these risks. In other words, while certain groups are more exposed to exclusion, this effect is partially mediated by socio-economic position, confirming the importance of adopting an intersectional and class-sensitive perspective in the analysis of older workers' labour market outcomes.

Moreover, our findings underscore the importance of institutional and contextual factors, typically referred to in the literature as push, maintain, and pull factors (Macken et al., 2022). For instance, in regions with lower GDP per capita, the labour market may lack the capacity to absorb or retain older workers. This structural constraint functions as a push factor, increasing the likelihood of prolonged inactivity. On the other hand, employment incentive programmes act as maintain factors, supporting older individuals in staying employed longer: where implemented, they are associated with lower rates of inactivity among the elderly. Finally, higher statutory retirement ages, while designed to extend working lives, may in fact result in a greater share of older individuals remaining in the category of inactive but not yet formally retired, particularly in contexts where re-employment opportunities are limited. Our results also indicate that stay-at-home measures reduced the rate of inactivity, while telework measures were linked with an increase in inactivity among elderly workers. We do find a statistically significant correlation between closures or activity bans during the pandemic and activity level.

Data

Our analysis relies on data extracted from the European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC), a cross-sectional and longitudinal sample survey coordinated by Eurostat. EU-SILC collects information from EU member states on income, poverty, social exclusion, and living conditions, along with detailed data on respondents' labour market participation. The survey covers all private households and their members residing in the country at the time of data collection. While data is gathered for all household members, only individuals aged 16 and above are interviewed. Sampling methods vary by country, with stratified multistage sampling being the most common approach. Depending on the country, respondent locations can be identified at the NUTS0, NUTS1, or NUTS2 level. As we are interested in the trajectories of older workers, we restrict our sample by keeping only respondents aged 50–70. In this way, we focus

on those approaching retirement age, individuals who might have exited the labour market but are still potentially "employable". Moreover, given that the longitudinal component of the EU-SILC has a smaller sample size than the cross-sectional component, we rely on the latter and treat the data as a pooled cross-section. As a result, our final dataset spans 27 countries (26 EU members states, except Germany, plus Norway) and 117 NUTS regions over the 2010–2022 period. Data on contextual variables such as regional GDP per capita have been extracted from the EUROSTAT Regional Database, while data on employment incentives and share of national GDP spent on Active Labour Market Policies (ALMP) have been extracted from the OECD database. Lastly, data on COVID-19 measures have been extracted from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control.

Data limitation

This study is subject to several important data limitations that we want to highlight both for a correct interpretation of the results that follow, but also to address future development of data collection strategies at the European level.

First, EU-SILC does not provide information on the reasons behind individuals' labour market exits or retirement decisions. As such, we are unable to distinguish between voluntary and involuntary retirement or inactivity, which limits our ability to assess the role of personal choice versus structural constraints in explaining older workers' labour market status. Second, as previously noted, the panel component of EU-SILC is extremely limited in length and scope. Due to these constraints, our analysis relies on cross-sectional data rather than panel data, which precludes a dynamic examination of individual employment trajectories over time. Third, we note a documented time-series break in the German EU-SILC data, which primarily affects income-related variables (see Eurostat, 2021). To address potential compatibility issues, we present our main models excluding Germany. Robustness checks including German data yield substantially similar estimates, suggesting that the exclusion does not significantly bias the results. Fourth, when analysing subnational data related to the COVID-19 pandemic, we encountered considerable missing data and inconsistencies in regional reporting, especially for the year 2022. While some datasets (e.g. Naqvi, 2021) offer subnational information on fatalities, overall coverage is variable, and many indicators (e.g. testing, hospitalizations, vaccination rates) are missing or inconsistently reported across countries and time periods. For instance, France provides data only at the national level in 2022, while regional data (NUTS1/NUTS2) are available for previous years. Similar inconsistencies affect the data for Germany, Finland, and Norway, where only national-level statistics are reported. These discrepancies limit the comparability of regional trends over time. While we harmonized the regional data as much as possible for the regression models, we report it in its original form in the descriptive statistics in order not to lose valuable information. Moreover, countries differ widely in terms of data accessibility, with some publishing detailed regional statistics via official portals, and others relying on third-party platforms like ArcGIS Hub or GitHub. For these reasons, we rely on national-level COVID-19 indicators from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) to investigate how the pandemic may have influenced older individuals' decisions to remain in or leave the labour force. While this approach sacrifices within-country variation, it ensures comparability and robustness across contexts.

Methodology

Our analysis adopts a multilevel modelling approach to examine the determinants of the risk of exiting from the labour market for older workers. In this case, individuals (i) are embedded

within European regions (j), classified at either the NUTS2 or NUTS1 level depending on data availability, over the 2010–2022-time span (t). Labour market attachments are shaped by both individual-level attributes (such as age, education, and gender) and broader structural factors (including regional economic conditions and national policies). Multilevel modelling explicitly accounts for this complexity, enabling us to disentangle the influence of both personal characteristics and contextual dynamics while respecting the nested nature of the data.

We implement a two-level multilevel model with random intercepts, where the levels are individual (i), and region (j), plus year fixed effects to control for factors changing each year that are common to all units for a given year.

To approximate labour market exit, we define our main outcome (Outcome 1) variable as a binary that equals 1 if the respondent is at risk of exclusion from the labour market. Specifically, it takes the value of 0 if the individual has spent at least 6-months in employment, unemployment, education, retirement (not-at-risk), and 1 otherwise (at-risk). As a robustness check, we also constructed a second version of the outcome variable (Outcome 2), that adopts a 12-months threshold to categorize those at risk of exclusion.

This definition captures individuals who are not participating in the labour market for a prolonged duration, distinguishing them from those with some form of labour market attachment, either because they work or they are actively looking for work, that is a mandatory condition to be considered unemployed according to the EUROSTAT definition. To note that the decision to include retirees in the *not-at-risk* group is justified because the goal is to approximate labour market exclusion, not simply inactivity. Retirement typically reflects a legitimate and institutionalized pathway out of the labour market, especially among older individuals, and thus should not be conflated with forms of exclusion that imply marginalization, disengagement, or involuntary detachment.

Among the controls, we include the sex of the respondent (as EU-SILC does not have information on gender), the marital status, if the respondent lives in a urban, peri-urban or rural context, the presence of a health-related limitation¹, the level of education, whether or not the respondent has caring responsibilities and domestic tasks² (defined with a dummy that takes the value of 1 if the respondent has spent 6 months or more in these activities in the last 12 months) and the level of wealth (proxied by country-year quintiles of taxes on wealth). Additionally, we added year dummies to control for macro-level year-specific.

Moreover, among the regional-level institutional characteristics, we include in the analysis one indicator for each of the three categories of factors commonly identified in the literature as

¹ This refers to question Ph030: Limitation in activities because of health problems. This is the variable that EUROSTAT recommends using it as an indication for disability.

² The variable on domestic tasks and care responsibilities was constructed based on EU-SILC question PL089: Number of months spent fulfilling domestic tasks, which respondents answer alongside a broader set of questions regarding how they spent the past 12 months. These same questions were also used to construct our outcome variable, making it likely that there is a strong correlation between reporting domestic and care responsibilities and being classified as inactive in our model. Due to this potential overlap, we conducted a robustness check in the results section by re-estimating the model without including the domestic tasks and care responsibilities variable among the regressors.

push, maintain, and pull factors related to older workers' exit from the labour market (Macken et al., 2022). Specifically:

- i. GDP per capita, as low levels of economic development can be understood as structural labour market constraints that involuntarily push older workers out of employment (*push factor*);
- ii. employment incentives, which are considered *maintain factors* as they support the retention of older workers in the labour market;
- iii. the statutory retirement age, included as a proxy for *pull factors*, namely institutional elements that encourage withdrawal from the labour force.

Therefore, our estimation equation is the following:

$$Y_{ijt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Sex}_{ijt} + \beta_2 \text{Marital}_{ijt} + \beta_3 \text{Rural}_{ijt} + \beta_4 \text{Limit}_{ijt} + \beta_5 \text{Domestic}_{ijt} + \beta_6 \text{Education}_{ijt} + \beta_7 \text{WealthTax}_{ijt} + \beta_8 \text{Year}_t + \gamma_1 \text{GDPpc}_{jt} + \gamma_2 \text{Emp_incentives}_{jt} + \gamma_3 \text{Formal_age}_{jt} + u_{jt} + \varepsilon_{ijt}$$

Where:

- Y_{ijt} is the outcome variable for labour market exclusion for individual i in region j
- Sex_{ijt} is the biological sex of the respondent
- Marital_{ijt} is the marital status of the respondent (single adult or couple)
- Rural_{ijt} is the living area (urban, peri-urban, or rural area)
- Limit_{ijt} is the health-related limitation (limited, not limited)
- Domestic_t is whether or not respondents have domestic tasks
- Education_{ijt} is the level of education (lower-secondary or less, secondary, and tertiary education)
- WealthTax_{ijt} is the quintiles of taxes paid on wealth (Lowest 20%, Second 20%, Middle 20%, Fourth 20%, Highest 20%)
- Year_t are year dummies
- GDPpc_{jt} is the regional GDP per capita
- $\text{Emp_incentives}_{jt}$ is the national % of GDP spent on employment incentives
- Formal_age_{jt} is the national retirement formal age
- u_{jt} is the random intercept for region j
- ε_{ijt} is the individual-level residual

For the Covid-sample analyses we are restricting our time series to the period 2019 - 2022 and additionally control for the number of cases at the NUTS2 level, or lowest available level using the data compiled by European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control.

To examine the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, we also estimate the model separately for 2020 and 2022, and test for differences in individual coefficients using z-tests. This allows us to assess whether and how the estimates change at the start and end of the pandemic. Furthermore, to explore the potential influence of containment measures, we re-estimate the model including additional contextual variables that approximate the intensity and effects of pandemic-related restrictions. Specifically, we control for the number of different COVID measures at the lowest available level using the data compiled by European Centre for Disease

Prevention and Control. We are differentiating between closures, or bans on events or public gatherings, adaptation of work or telework measures, and stay at home orders. These types of measure are chosen as they both may affect one’s possibilities to participate in the labour market, but also one’s willingness to do so.

Lastly, we examine how labour market exclusion is shaped by the social gradient, as outlined in the introduction. In particular, we aim to explore whether the effect of certain characteristics associated with a higher likelihood of exiting the labour market is mediated by individuals’ social class, proxied here by wealth quintiles. We do that by introducing some interaction effects between socio-demographic characteristics that are associated with a more vulnerable position in the labour market and wealth quintile, as in the following equations:

iv. Interaction between health-related limitations and wealth

$$Y_{ijt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Sex}_{ijt} + \beta_2 \text{Marital}_{ijt} + \beta_3 \text{Rural}_{ijt} + \beta_4 \text{Limit}_{ijt} * \text{WealthTax}_{ijt} + \beta_5 \text{Domestic}_{ijt} + \beta_6 \text{Education}_{ijt} + \gamma_1 \text{GDPpc}_{jt} + \gamma_2 \text{Emp_incentives}_{jt} + \gamma_3 \text{Formal_age}_{jt} + u_{jt} + \epsilon_{ijt}$$

ii. Interaction between domestic tasks and wealth

$$Y_{ijt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Sex}_{ijt} + \beta_2 \text{Marital}_{ijt} + \beta_3 \text{Rural}_{ijt} + \beta_4 \text{Limit}_{ijt} + \beta_5 \text{Domestic}_{ijt} * \text{WealthTax}_{ijt} + \beta_6 \text{Education}_{ijt} + \gamma_1 \text{GDPpc}_{jt} + \gamma_2 \text{Emp_incentives}_{jt} + \gamma_3 \text{Formal_age}_{jt} + u_{jt} + \epsilon_{ijt}$$

iii. Interaction between biological sex and wealth

$$Y_{ijt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Sex}_{ijt} * \text{WealthTax}_{ijt} + \beta_2 \text{Marital}_{ijt} + \beta_3 \text{Rural}_{ijt} + \beta_4 \text{Limit}_{ijt} + \beta_5 \text{Domestic}_{ijt} + \beta_6 \text{Education}_{ijt} + \gamma_1 \text{GDPpc}_{jt} + \gamma_2 \text{Emp_incentives}_{jt} + \gamma_3 \text{Formal_age}_{jt} + u_{jt} + \epsilon_{ijt}$$

Descriptive statistics

Table 1 reports descriptive statistics for the overall sample and by outcome variables. From the descriptives, we see that the majority of respondents are classified as not-at-risk (86.2%), while 13.0% fall into the *at-risk* group. Interestingly, women make up 76.0% of the *at-risk* group, despite accounting for 52.7% of the total sample. No big differences emerge if we decompose by marital status or milieu, but we see that respondents with health-related limitations tend to fall more frequently in the at-risk category (58.7%). Low education (no or only primary education) is much more prevalent among the at-risk (28.0%) than among the not-at-risk (10.9%), while tertiary education is found in 24.4% of not-at-risk, but only 8.6% of at-risk individuals. Care responsibilities are widespread among individuals classified as at-risk³. Lastly, the share of *at-risk* individuals drops steadily in higher quintiles.

³ This variable (PI089): originates from a set of questions that capture how respondents spent their time during the year preceding the survey, and it is therefore likely to be highly correlated with our outcome variables. Given its conceptual relevance, we chose to retain it in the analysis—acknowledging that its inclusion may introduce selection bias or multicollinearity, particularly due to its potential overlap with inactivity patterns. That said, in the regressions that follow, the results remain robust even when this variable is excluded.

Table 4 Descriptive findings for the overall sample and by the Outcome 1 variable.

	Not-at-risk	At-risk	Total
N (%)	1,836,090 (86.2%)	277,173 (13.0%)	2,129,549 (100.0%)
Respondent sex			
Male	931,895 (50.8%)	66,556 (24.0%)	1,008,110 (47.3%)
Female	904,189 (49.2%)	210,617 (76.0%)	1,121,431 (52.7%)
Marital status			
Single adult	473,431 (25.8%)	73,790 (26.6%)	548,933 (25.9%)
Couple	1,361,930 (74.2%)	203,163 (73.4%)	1,568,676 (74.1%)
Milieu			
Urban	565,320 (34.6%)	86,301 (33.2%)	657,731 (34.4%)
Periurban	447,065 (27.3%)	70,844 (27.3%)	521,761 (27.3%)
Rural	623,018 (38.1%)	102,823 (39.6%)	732,102 (38.3%)
Health-related limitations			
No	971,367 (61.0%)	105,483 (41.3%)	1,076,989 (58.3%)
Yes	620,314 (39.0%)	150,089 (58.7%)	770,882 (41.7%)
If spent months in domestic tasks and care responsibilities			
No	1,828,240 (99.8%)	137,988 (50.0%)	1,966,228 (93.3%)
Yes	3,280 (0.2%)	137,743 (50.0%)	141,023 (6.7%)
Education			
No education	15,137 (0.8%)	8,926 (3.3%)	24,095 (1.2%)
Primary education	183,163 (10.1%)	67,190 (24.7%)	250,517 (12.0%)
Lower secondary	303,041 (16.7%)	71,195 (26.1%)	374,659 (18.0%)
Upper secondary	805,279 (44.5%)	95,055 (34.9%)	901,229 (43.2%)
Post-secondary/non tertiary	62,872 (3.5%)	6,701 (2.5%)	69,646 (3.3%)
Tertiary education	441,676 (24.4%)	23,495 (8.6%)	465,767 (22.3%)
Disposable income quintile			
Lowest 20%	812,996 (45.8%)	155,050 (57.8%)	973,025 (47.2%)
Second 20%	189,180 (10.7%)	25,878 (9.7%)	217,484 (10.6%)
Middle 20%	238,858 (13.5%)	29,463 (11.0%)	270,990 (13.2%)
Fourth 20%	254,848 (14.4%)	29,673 (11.1%)	287,420 (14.0%)
Highest 20%	279,536 (15.7%)	27,971 (10.4%)	310,647 (15.1%)

Note: Comma (,) used as number separator, while a period is used a decimal separator. NB Germany excluded.

Source: Authors' elaboration based on EU-SILC data

Descriptive patterns during the COVID19 pandemic

The provided data illustrates the yearly distribution of our main outcome variable, at-risk of labour market exclusion, in the subsample from 2019 to 2022, with a total summary across the

four years. These results are presented in *Table 2*. Overall, despite the pandemic, we find relatively small fluctuations in the share of persons who are at-risk of exclusion from the labour market. This holds true both for the 6-months (outcome 1) and 12-months (outcome 2) threshold variables. In 2019, the percentage of individuals was 12.6%, which slightly decreased to 11.6% in 2020—the year COVID-19 emerged globally. This trend continued with minor fluctuations, reaching 11.3% in 2021 and 11.5% in 2022.

Table 5 Changes in share of individuals who have spent at least six months in employment, unemployment, education, retirement during the 2019-2022 period. EU-SILC 28 countries, subsample 50-70 years of age.

	2019	2020	2021	2022	Total
Outcome 1					
0	153,807 (87.4%)	142,281 (88.4%)	152,194 (88.7%)	158,238 (88.3%)	452,713 (88.5%)
1	22,246 (12.6%)	18,750 (11.6%)	19,333 (11.3%)	20,936 (11.7%)	59,019 (11.5%)
Outcome 2					
0	151,750 (86.2%)	141,043 (87.6%)	150,728 (87.9%)	155,761 (86.9%)	447,532 (87.5%)
1	24,303 (13.8%)	19,988 (12.4%)	20,799 (12.1%)	23,412 (13.1%)	64,199 (12.5%)

Source: Authors' elaboration based on EU-SILC data

Despite the data limitations outlined in previous sections, *Figure 1* shows important subnational differences in risk of exclusion from the labour market, not only between the countries studied, but also within the countries. Spain, Italy and Poland are the most prominent examples of regional differences in labour market inactivity amongst elderly workers. These differences are smaller in France, and Germany, but still visible. In sum, the figure showcases a descriptive illustration of why subregional differences in labour market activity should be accounted for.

Figure 1: Activity status over between 2019 and 2022 at the regional level. EU-SILC.

To better understand the impact of the pandemic we are employing national-level COVID-19 indicators from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). Our indicators capture the number of enacted COVID-related measures with a specific aim. We differentiate between closures, or bans on events or public gatherings, adaptation of work or telework measures, and stay at home orders. These types of measures are chosen as they both may affect one’s possibilities to participate in the labour market, but also one’s willingness to do so.

Figure 2: Types of measures, aggregated per country. More intense colours represent new or additional measures. Data from ECDP.

The distribution of the number of measures is presented in *Figure 2*. In each panel of the figure, we present the number of individual measures with a policy-area implemented in each country. The figures do not necessarily reflect whether the measures were invasive. The number of measures reflects both partial and total closures or bans. Overall, the data indicates that although all countries implemented closures or bans on public gatherings, there have been relatively fewer measures related to work or teleworking, as well as stay-at-home orders. Italy is one of the countries with most measures implemented in all fields. Germany, Norway and Sweden on the other hand implemented fewer measures across. For instance, Norway and Germany are the countries with fewest measures regarding work or telework, while Romania and Poland had slightly fewer measures. These indicators also reflect the country's need to adapt and change policies. This is especially clear for Italy, where policies changed rather frequently due to the intensity of the pandemic and high mortality rate. The figure also illustrates that EU-countries also had different strategies to limit contact between individuals, and countries more often changed measures regarding closures and bans, compared to telework. This latter observation may imply that at-risk persons in public facing jobs were more likely to be affected by the pandemic, compared to those in jobs where telework was a meaningful alternative.

Results

In *Table 6* below we report results from the main analysis. Model 1 reports results from the intercept-only, Model 2 displays results with the whole set of individual covariates, in Model 3 and 4 we add contextual level variables, and in Model 5 and 6 we report estimates for the pre- and post-pandemic period (2019 and 2022).

Several interesting findings about socio-demographic determinants emerge. Elderly women tend to be more at risk of labour market exclusion overall. Interestingly, the female coefficient stops to be significant with the pandemic, suggesting a shift in gender-related dynamics. This shift might be correlated with the introduction of anti-Covid measures, which will be discussed in our next subsection.

Being part of a couple is associated with lower risk of labour market exclusion, whereas living in a single-adult household is positively correlated with it. Health-related limitations consistently increase the likelihood of being at risk across all model specifications (as in Humphrey et al., 2003, Dantas et al, 2017). On this, one possible explanation is that older workers in poor health may face greater discrimination in hiring or retention, as employers may perceive them as less productive or more costly in terms of accommodations and absenteeism. Higher levels of education and belonging to wealthier income quintiles are both associated with a lower probability of labour market exclusion, similar to what was found in Schuring et al. (2013). This is likely not only due to better employment prospects or stronger social capital, but more crucially because individuals with higher education or greater wealth are often employed in less physically demanding, more rewarding, and higher-status occupations. These jobs tend to offer

better working conditions, greater autonomy, and more opportunities for meaningful engagement, which can encourage longer participation in the labour market.

Finally, having care responsibilities is linked to an increased risk of being excluded from the labour market for old individuals. This is particularly relevant in contexts where formal care services are limited, and family-based caregiving continues into later life. Older workers with caregiving duties may find it difficult to reconcile these responsibilities with labour market demands, leading to sustained inactivity.

As a robustness check, i) we checked that these results hold true also if we exclude care responsibilities from the covariates (for the reasons explained in footnote 2); this allows us to verify whether the inclusion of this variable substantially affects the estimated relationships or inflates the association with the outcome due to shared measurement context, and ii) we use the second version of our outcome variable, i.e., the one that adopts a 12-months threshold to categorize those at risk of exclusion (Model 3 in *Table 6* and *Table A5* in the Appendix).

As for the contextual-level variables, the findings align with theoretical expectations. Economic development, proxied by regional GDP per capita, is significantly associated with a lower risk of labour market exclusion among older workers. This supports the notion that economically dynamic regions provide more opportunities and institutional support, thereby acting as a “pull” factor that fosters labour market participation in later life. In other words, in richer areas, older individuals may find it easier to remain employed or to re-enter the labour market due to better job availability.

Moreover, employment incentives, such as hiring subsidies or wage support schemes, show a strong and negative association with the risk of inactivity, suggesting their effectiveness in promoting attachment to the labour market of the elderly. Crucially, this relationship holds even when controlling for the country-specific formal retirement age, which often represents a structural determinant of older workers' labour force participation. This indicates that policy instruments can actively shape individual outcomes, even within institutional constraints like retirement age thresholds.

Lastly, when comparing the pre- and post-pandemic periods, no substantial differences emerge in the estimated coefficients⁴, with two exceptions. First, the female coefficient becomes statistically insignificant in 2022, while the coefficient for employment incentives is not significant in 2019, but it grows and becomes significant after the pandemic. This shift suggests that employment incentives may have played a more prominent and effective role in mitigating labour market exclusion in the aftermath of the crisis, possibly due to their expansion or increased relevance in the context of disrupted employment trajectories.

⁴ We formally test the differences in coefficients using z-tests, which reveal no significant changes for the other variables.

Table 6 Regression results of multilevel models. Outcome 1: 0 if the individual has spent at least 6-months in employment, unemployment, education, retirement (not-at-risk), and 1 otherwise (at-risk)

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
VARIABLES	Base	Base with controls	Base without care	With contextual	2019	2022
Female		0.005*** (0.000)	0.133*** (0.001)	0.009*** (0.001)	0.005*** (0.002)	-0.000 (0.002)
Couple		-0.025*** (0.000)	0.024*** (0.001)	-0.024*** (0.000)	-0.032*** (0.002)	-0.028*** (0.002)
Rural		0.004*** (0.000)	0.004*** (0.000)	0.004*** (0.000)	0.004*** (0.001)	0.007*** (0.001)
Limitation		0.121*** (0.000)	0.115*** (0.001)	0.126*** (0.000)	0.128*** (0.002)	0.120*** (0.002)
Primary education		-0.068*** (0.002)	-0.088*** (0.002)	-0.074*** (0.002)	-0.083*** (0.006)	-0.093*** (0.006)
Lower secondary		-0.080*** (0.002)	-0.140*** (0.002)	-0.094*** (0.002)	-0.102*** (0.006)	-0.104*** (0.006)
Upper secondary		-0.098*** (0.002)	-0.190*** (0.002)	-0.114*** (0.002)	-0.123*** (0.006)	-0.127*** (0.006)
Post-secondary non tertiary		-0.112*** (0.002)	-0.229*** (0.003)	-0.126*** (0.002)	-0.134*** (0.007)	-0.139*** (0.007)
Tertiary education		-0.124*** (0.002)	-0.254*** (0.002)	-0.140*** (0.002)	-0.146*** (0.006)	-0.143*** (0.006)
Wealth taxes, Second 20%		-0.015*** (0.001)	-0.017*** (0.001)	-0.013*** (0.001)	-0.006** (0.003)	-0.013*** (0.003)
Wealth taxes, Middle 20%		-0.017*** (0.001)	-0.020*** (0.001)	-0.018*** (0.001)	-0.011*** (0.003)	-0.014*** (0.002)
Wealth taxes, Fourth 20%		-0.018*** (0.001)	-0.022*** (0.001)	-0.019*** (0.001)	-0.010*** (0.002)	-0.019*** (0.002)
Wealth taxes, Highest 20%		-0.016*** (0.001)	-0.017*** (0.001)	-0.018*** (0.001)	-0.007*** (0.002)	-0.019*** (0.002)
If spent at least 6 months in domestic tasks and care responsibilities		0.903*** (0.001)		0.895*** (0.001)	0.908*** (0.003)	0.901*** (0.003)
GDP per capita				-0.076*** (0.004)	0.004 (0.013)	-0.012 (0.011)
Employment incentives				-0.016*** (0.002)	-0.016 (0.050)	-0.090** (0.041)
Formal age of retirement				0.004*** (0.000)	0.005*** (0.001)	0.005*** (0.001)
Constant	0.132***	0.159***	0.204***	0.629***	-0.203	-0.005

	(0.006)	(0.004)	(0.006)	(0.040)	(0.144)	(0.119)
Observations	2,113,263	1,687,884	1,690,551	1,300,513	123,572	107,058
Number of groups	116	111	111	98	98	70
Level 2	Region	Region	Region	Region	Region	Region

Note: Comma (,) used as number separator, while a period is used a decimal separator. NB Germany excluded.

Source: Authors' elaboration based on EU-SILC data

We then proceed to examine some interaction effects among individual characteristics of respondents. Specifically, we want to explore how certain characteristics that are associated with a higher probability of exiting from the labour market are mediated by the belonging to a certain social class (here proxied by quintiles of wealth). In *Table 7* below, we examine the interaction effects between quintiles of wealth and having a limitation (Model 1), having domestic tasks and care responsibilities (Model 2) and gender (Model 3).

The results confirm previous findings: *per se*, being a woman, having a health-related limitation, and engaging in care responsibilities are all associated with a higher likelihood of being excluded from the labour market. Conversely, individuals in higher income quintiles are significantly less likely to be at risk. Importantly, the results highlight the moderating effect of wealth. The negative impact of health limitations on labour market participation is substantially mitigated by wealth level: older individuals with health-related limitations who belong to wealthier social strata are less likely to be excluded compared to their lower-wealth counterparts. A similar pattern emerges for women: wealthier women are significantly less at risk of exclusion than those in the lower tax wealth quintiles. This suggests that economic resources buffer the effects of both gender and health disadvantage on elderly individuals. However, our models cannot exclude reverse causality – namely having more wealth is due to a higher propensity to be employed, even if we decided to rely on a wealth-related measure precisely to mitigate concerns about reverse causality. Indeed, we believe that these are less sensitive to short-term labour market fluctuations and better capture long-term socioeconomic positioning, thereby helping to reduce potential endogeneity between economic status and labour market participation.

An especially notable finding emerges from the interaction between caregiving responsibilities and income quintiles. The interaction terms display positive and increasing coefficients, indicating that old and wealthier individuals with domestic or caregiving responsibilities are more likely to exit the labour market. This may reflect greater capacity to “opt out”: those in higher wealth groups can afford to withdraw from employment to focus on care duties without facing economic insecurity. In contrast, less wealthy individuals, even when burdened with care responsibilities, often lack this option and must remain in the labour market out of necessity.

These findings underscore the role of economic inequality as a key determinant of labour market exclusion in later life. While factors such as gender, health, and caregiving responsibilities increase vulnerability, it is primarily financial resources that determine whether these challenges result in actual detachment from the labour market.

Table 7 Interactions between quintiles of wealth and having a limitation (Model 1), having domestic tasks and care responsibilities (Model 2) and gender (Model 3). between key indicators. Multi-level models. Outcome 1: 0 if the individual has spent at least 6-months in employment, unemployment, education, retirement (not-at-risk), and 1 otherwise (at-risk)

VARIABLES	(1) Limitation* Wealth	(4) Domestic tasks* Wealth	(7) Female* Wealth
Female	0.005*** (0.000)	0.005*** (0.000)	0.011*** (0.001)
Limitation	0.134*** (0.001)	0.120*** (0.000)	0.121*** (0.000)
If spent at least 6 months in domestic tasks and care responsibilities	0.903*** (0.001)	0.894*** (0.001)	0.903*** (0.001)
Wealth taxes, Second 20%	-0.014*** (0.001)	-0.016*** (0.001)	-0.003*** (0.001)
Wealth taxes, Middle 20%	-0.011*** (0.001)	-0.018*** (0.001)	-0.009*** (0.001)
Wealth taxes, Fourth 20%	-0.008*** (0.001)	-0.020*** (0.001)	-0.013*** (0.001)
Wealth taxes, Highest 20%	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.018*** (0.001)	-0.013*** (0.001)
Wealth taxes, Second 20%*Limitation	-0.002 (0.001)		
Wealth taxes, Middle 20% *Limitation	-0.017*** (0.001)		
Wealth taxes, Fourth 20% *Limitation	-0.031*** (0.001)		
Wealth taxes, Highest 20% *Limitation	-0.051*** (0.001)		
Wealth taxes, Second 20%*Domestic tasks		0.011*** (0.003)	
Wealth taxes, Middle 20% *Domestic tasks		0.018*** (0.002)	
Wealth taxes, Fourth 20% *Domestic tasks		0.023*** (0.002)	
Wealth taxes, Highest 20% *Domestic tasks		0.033*** (0.002)	
Wealth taxes, Second 20%* Female			-0.021*** (0.001)
Wealth taxes, Middle 20% * Female			-0.014*** (0.001)

Wealth taxes, Fourth 20% * Female			-0.009*** (0.001)
Wealth taxes, Highest 20% * Female			-0.006*** (0.001)
Constant	0.152*** (0.004)	0.160*** (0.004)	0.155*** (0.004)
Observations	1,687,884	1,687,884	1,687,884
Number of groups	111	111	111
Level 2	Region	Region	Region

Note: Comma (,) used as number separator, while a period is used a decimal separator. NB Germany excluded.

Source: Authors' elaboration based on EU-SILC data

In the following set of models, we additionally include controls for the number of bans, or closures, stay-at-home, and work from home or telework measures in addition to the controls presented in the previous sets of models. The individual-level results confirm the patterns discussed previously in this section (from models 4, 5 and 6 from *Table 6*). These results are presented in *Table 8*. This implies that the individual-level drivers of inactivity: being a woman, having a health-related limitation, lower income, and engaging in care responsibilities are all associated with a higher likelihood of being excluded from the labour market, also when accounting for the number of stay-at-home, bans or closures and telework measures. Additional analyses also show that the interactions between health limitation and wealth, as well as wealth and sex also hold when the COVID-19 measures are included.

Table 8 Selected results on the impact of Covid-indicators. Outcome 1: 0 if the individual has spent at least 6-months in employment, unemployment, education, retirement (not-at-risk), and 1 otherwise (at-risk)

VARIABLES	Model 1 2020	Model 2 2021	Model 3 2022
Telework measures	-0,036* (0.021)	-0,036* (0.021)	0,030*** (0.004)
Closures, bans	-0,004 (0,004)	-0,004 (0,004)	0,004 (0.003)
Stay-at-home	0,000 (0,006)	0,000 (0,006)	-0,017*** (0,004)
Individual-level controls	Sex, couple, rural, health limitation, education level, wealth taxes		
Level 2	Region	Region	Region
Level 2 – controls	GDP per capita, unemployment level		
Num.Obs.	178599	178599	204835
Std.Errors	Robust - HC3	Robust - HC3	Robust - HC3

p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01

Note: Comma (,) used as number separator, while a period is used a decimal separator.

Source: Authors' elaboration based on EU-SILC data and data from the ECDC.

Telework measures are associated with a slight reduction in the likelihood of labour market exclusion for elderly workers during 2020 and 2021. While the association is modest, it suggests that telework policies provided some protection for elderly workers by enabling them to remain employed or engaged in the labour market during the pandemic. However, in 2022, a higher number of telework measures are associated with a small increase in the likelihood of labour market exclusion for elderly workers. This may reflect a shift in the labour market dynamics as telework became more normalized, the skills required to adequately participate increased, although the technology was relatively user-friendly and accessible, and elderly workers may have faced challenges adapting to increasingly digital work environments in the long term. However, more research is needed to determine how elderly workers adopted new technologies and what challenges they may face.

The results also indicate that the number of stay-at-home orders were not significantly associated with labour market exclusion for elderly workers in 2020 and 2021. However, in 2022, stay-at-home orders are associated with a small decrease in the likelihood of labour market exclusion for elderly workers, on average.

We do not find statistically significant association between closure and bans in any of the three pandemic years (2020, 2021, and 2022). Closures and bans do not appear to have a substantial impact on labour market exclusion for elderly workers. This could indicate that these measures affected other groups more significantly (e.g., younger workers or workers in specific sectors) or that elderly workers were less exposed to these disruptions. Furthermore, it is also important to

underline that all countries included in this study had at least 5 closure or ban measures enacted and that there is little variation on this indicator, which may also explain why we do not find any impact of these measures with the current study design.

Table 9 Interactions limitations, telework and stay-at-home measures. Outcome 1: 0 if the individual has spent at least 6-months in employment, unemployment, education, retirement (not-at-risk), and 1 otherwise (at-risk)

	Interaction limitation x telework		Interaction limitation x stay-at-home	
	2020	2022	2020	2022
Limitation	0,066*** (0,002)	0,046*** (0,001)	0,047*** (0,002)	0,047*** (0,001)
Telework	-0,001* (0,000)	-0,005*** (0,001)	-0,004*** (0,000)	-0,004*** (0,001)
Stay-at-home	0,002*** (0,000)	-0,038*** (0,002)	0,001*** (0,000)	-0,020*** (0,002)
Limitation× telework	-0,006*** (-0,001)	0,003 (-0,002)		
Limitation x stay-at-home			0,002*** (-0,001)	-0,037*** (-0,003)
Num.Obs.	178599	204835	178599	204835
Individual-level controls	Sex, couple, rural, health limitation, education level, wealth taxes			
Level 2	Region + controls for GDP per capita and unemployment			

• p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01

Note: Comma (,) used as number separator, while a period is used a decimal separator.

Source: Authors' elaboration based on EU-SILC data and data from the ECDC

Additional analyses also show that these associations are heterogenous, presented in *Table 9* and *Table 10*. For elderly workers with health limitations, the results indicate that telework measures were associated with a slight reduction in the likelihood of labour market exclusion in 2020. This suggests that telework policies provided a protective effect for elderly workers with health limitations in 2020, likely by enabling them to work remotely and avoid workplace exposure to COVID-19 risks. In 2022, there is no statistically significant relationship between telework measures and labour market exclusion for individuals with health limitations. This indicates that telework may have become less impactful for this group, potentially because telework was normalized or because the needs of workers with health-related limitations were not adequately addressed as the pandemic evolved.

For individuals with health limitations, stay-at-home orders in 2020 were associated with a small but statistically significant increase in the likelihood of labour market exclusion, suggesting that stay-at-home orders may have disproportionately affected workers with health limitations, potentially because they were more likely to face challenges transitioning to remote work or

because they were employed in sectors that were more severely disrupted by these policies. By 2022, stay-at-home orders were associated with a significant reduction in the likelihood of labour market exclusion for individuals with health limitations. This suggests either a more successful adaptation over time, where these workers may have become better supported by the enacted policies, or employers may have implemented measures to accommodate their needs during periods of stay-at-home orders.

Table 10 Interactions limitations, telework and stay-at-home measures. Outcome 1: 0 if the individual has spent at least 6-months in employment, unemployment, education, retirement (not-at-risk), and 1 otherwise (at-risk)

	Interaction limitation x telework		Interaction limitation x stay-at-home	
	2020	2022	2020	2022
Female	0.005*** (0.001)	0.005*** (0.001)	-0.023*** (0.002)	0.004*** (0.001)
Telework	0.003** (0.002)	0.003** (0.002)	-0.004*** (0.000)	-0.004*** (0.001)
Stay-at-home	-0.038*** (0.002)	-0.038*** (0.002)	-0.001*** (0.000)	-0.033*** (0.002)
Female x telework	-0.013*** (0.002)	-0.013*** (0.002)		
Female x stay-at-home			0.007*** (0.001)	-0.010*** (0.003)
Num.Obs.	204835	204835	178599	204835
Individual-level controls	Sex, couple, rural, health limitation, education level, wealth taxes			
Level 2	Region + controls for GDP per capita and unemployment			

Note: Comma (,) used as number separator, while a period is used a decimal separator.

Source: Authors' elaboration based on EU-SILC data and data from the ECDC.

For women, telework measures in 2020 were associated with a small but statistically significant reduction in the likelihood of labour market exclusion compared to men. This suggests that telework policies provided may have offered some protection for women. The “protective” impact of telework for women persisted in 2022, with telework measures continuing to reduce the likelihood of their labour market exclusion, potentially because remote work allowed women to balance work and caregiving responsibilities. We cannot fully exclude that these associations can be at least partly explained by men and women working in different jobs, or sectors of the economy. However, for women, stay-at-home orders in 2020 were associated with a small but statistically significant increase in the likelihood of labour market exclusion compared to men. This suggests that stay-at-home orders disproportionately impacted women at the start of the pandemic. By 2022, stay-at-home orders were associated with a small but statistically significant reduction in the likelihood of labour market exclusion for women,

compared to men. This shift suggests that over time, women may have adapted to the constraints of stay-at-home orders, or that structural changes (e.g., more flexible work arrangements) may have mitigated the negative impact of these policies on women.

Concluding remarks

From our results, some interesting evidence emerges about determinants of labour market exclusion among older individuals, with clear implications for both policy and practice. Gender, household structure, health, education, and wealth emerge as central drivers of exclusion, often interacting in complex ways. For instance, elderly women are, in general, more vulnerable to exclusion and, as expected, health-related limitations consistently increase the risk of exclusion, reinforcing long-standing evidence that poor health is a significant barrier to continued labour force participation in later life. Socioeconomic status—particularly education and wealth—plays a crucial buffering role. Interestingly, wealth appears to mitigate other vulnerabilities as well: the negative effects of both poor health and gender disadvantage are significantly reduced among individuals with greater economic resources. These findings align with a broader life-course perspective, showing how economic privilege accumulates and shields individuals from later-life exclusion.

Importantly, our analysis also shows that policy measures introduced during the COVID-19 pandemic had heterogeneous effects, depending on individual characteristics. Telework policies, for example, appear to have offered meaningful protection for women and individuals with health limitations in 2020, by enabling continued participation in the labour market while avoiding health risks. However, this protective effect weakens by 2022, perhaps due to inadequate support for their evolving needs, or because telework became the new norm rather than an adaptive policy tool. Stay-at-home orders, on the other hand, were initially associated with increased exclusion for both women and individuals with health conditions, likely because of greater exposure to sectoral shutdowns and caregiving burdens. Yet, by 2022, these same policies are linked to reduced exclusion, suggesting that individuals and employers may have gradually adapted through structural changes and policy adjustments. Taken together, these results underscore the importance of intersectional and adaptive policy responses: while structural vulnerabilities persist, well-designed interventions—particularly those that enhance flexibility, inclusion, and support for care responsibilities—can play a decisive role in protecting older workers from marginalisation in times of crisis and beyond.

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Appendix

Table A1 Multinomial logistic regression of labour-market exit on age, education, helping others, loneliness and self-rated health, for men (Wave 8).

	B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% CI for Exp(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Voluntary exit Intercept	12.80	0.85	227.84	1	<.001			
Age	0.21	0.01	328.69	1	<.001	1.23	1.20	1.26
Years of education	-0.05	0.01	17.85	1	<.001	0.95	0.93	0.97
Not helping others the day before	-0.24	0.12	4.45	1	0.04	0.79	0.63	0.98
Less than 30 minutes helping others the day before	-0.61	0.19	10.49	1	0.00	0.54	0.38	0.79
Between 30 and 60 minutes helping others the day before	-0.18	0.16	1.31	1	0.25	0.83	0.61	1.14
More than 60 minutes helping others the day before (Ref. category)								
Not lonely	-0.27	0.34	0.64	1	0.42	0.76	0.39	1.49
Sometimes lonely	-0.47	0.36	1.63	1	0.20	0.63	0.31	1.28
Often or always lonely (Ref. category)								
Excellent self-rated health	-0.79	0.33	5.60	1	0.02	0.46	0.24	0.87
Very good self-rated health	-0.51	0.31	2.76	1	0.10	0.60	0.33	1.10
Good self-rated health	-0.32	0.30	1.10	1	0.29	0.73	0.40	1.32
Fair self-rated health	-0.81	0.32	6.54	1	0.01	0.45	0.24	0.83
Poor self-rated health (Ref. category)								
No partner in the household	0.10	0.14	0.56	1	0.46	1.11	0.85	1.45
Having a partner in the household (Ref. category)								

Involuntary exit	Intercept	0.08	1.42	0.00	1	0.96			
	Age	0.02	0.02	1.04	1	0.31	1.02	0.98	1.07
	Years of education	-0.07	0.02	11.15	1	<.001	0.93	0.89	0.97
	Not helping others the day before	-0.42	0.20	4.43	1	0.04	0.66	0.45	0.97
	Less than 30 minutes helping others the day before	-0.64	0.33	3.71	1	0.05	0.53	0.28	1.01
	Between 30 and 60 minutes helping others the day before	-0.28	0.28	0.99	1	0.32	0.76	0.44	1.31
	More than 60 minutes helping others the day before (Ref. category)								
	Not lonely	-0.90	0.41	4.71	1	0.03	0.41	0.18	0.92
	Sometimes lonely	-0.46	0.44	1.09	1	0.30	0.63	0.27	1.50
	Often or always lonely (Ref. category)								
	Excellent self-rated health	-3.86	0.64	36.29	1	<.001	0.02	0.01	0.07
	Very good self-rated health	-2.54	0.34	57.67	1	<.001	0.08	0.04	0.15
	Good self-rated health	-2.15	0.30	51.06	1	<.001	0.12	0.06	0.21
	Fair self-rated health	-1.55	0.31	25.75	1	<.001	0.21	0.12	0.39
	Poor self-rated health (Ref. category)								
	No partner in the household	0.12	0.23	0.28	1	0.60	1.13	0.72	1.77
	Having a partner in the household (Ref. category)								

Table A2 Nominal regression of labour market exit on age, education, helping others, loneliness, self-rated health, for women (Wave 8).

		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% CI for Exp(B)	
								Lower	Upper
Voluntary exit	Intercept	15.86	0.86	342.90	1	<.001			
	Age in 2020	0.25	0.01	440.77	1	<.001	1.29	1.26	1.32
	Years of education	-0.05	0.01	19.64	1	<.001	0.95	0.93	0.97
	Not helping others the day before	-0.24	0.10	5.49	1	0.02	0.79	0.65	0.96
	Less than 30 minutes helping others the day before	-0.57	0.22	6.71	1	0.01	0.56	0.37	0.87
	Between 30 and 60 minutes helping others the day before	-0.28	0.17	2.64	1	0.10	0.76	0.54	1.06
	More than 60 minutes helping others the day before (Ref. category)								
	Not lonely	-0.07	0.26	0.08	1	0.78	0.93	0.56	1.55
	Sometimes lonely	-0.01	0.28	0.00	1	0.97	0.99	0.58	1.70
	Often or always lonely (Ref. category)								
	Excellent self-rated health	-0.23	0.34	0.46	1	0.50	0.80	0.41	1.54
	Very good self-rated health	-0.26	0.32	0.64	1	0.43	0.77	0.41	1.46
	Good self-rated health	-0.19	0.32	0.35	1	0.56	0.83	0.44	1.55
	Fair self-rated health	-0.39	0.33	1.40	1	0.24	0.68	0.36	1.29
	Poor self-rated health (Ref. category)								
No partner in the household	-0.40	0.11	13.00	1	<.001	0.67	0.54	0.84	
Having a partner in the household (Ref. category)									
Involuntary exit	Intercept	0.38	1.37	0.08	1	0.78			
	Age in 2020	0.01	0.02	0.06	1	0.80	1.01	0.96	1.05
	Years of education	-0.05	0.02	6.45	1	0.01	0.95	0.91	0.99
	Not helping others the day before	0.02	0.18	0.01	1	0.92	1.02	0.71	1.45
	Less than 30 minutes helping others the day before	0.13	0.33	0.15	1	0.69	1.14	0.60	2.15
	Between 30 and 60 minutes helping others the day before	-0.18	0.32	0.31	1	0.58	0.84	0.45	1.56

More than 60 minutes helping others the day before (Ref. category)								
Not lonely	-0.90	0.30	9.19	1	0.00	0.41	0.23	0.73
Sometimes lonely	-0.54	0.32	2.81	1	0.09	0.58	0.31	1.10
Often or always lonely (Ref. category)								
Excellent self-rated health	-2.54	0.42	36.16	1	<.001	0.08	0.04	0.18
Very good self-rated health	-2.81	0.36	61.71	1	<.001	0.06	0.03	0.12
Good self-rated health	-1.94	0.30	41.30	1	<.001	0.14	0.08	0.26
Fair self-rated health	-1.15	0.30	14.57	1	<.001	0.32	0.18	0.57
Poor self-rated health (Ref. category)								
No partner in the household	-0.04	0.19	0.05	1	0.82	0.96	0.67	1.38
Having a partner in the household (Ref. category)								

Table A3 Nominal regression of labour market exit on age, education, helping others, loneliness and self-rated health, for men (Wave 9).

		B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% CI for Exp(B)		
								Lower	Upper	
Voluntary exit	Intercept	14.08	0.93	228.21	1	<.001				
	Age	0.23	0.01	299.64	1	<.001	1.26	1.23	1.29	
	Years of education	-0.04	0.01	9.48	1	0.00	0.96	0.94	0.99	
	Not helping others the day before	-0.39	0.12	10.84	1	<.001	0.68	0.54	0.86	
	Less than 30 minutes helping others the day before	-0.31	0.19	2.66	1	0.10	0.73	0.50	1.07	
	Between 30 and 60 minutes helping others the day before	-0.36	0.17	4.41	1	0.04	0.70	0.50	0.98	
	More than 60 minutes helping others the day before (Ref. category)									
	Not lonely	-0.08	0.35	0.06	1	0.81	0.92	0.46	1.84	
	Sometimes lonely	0.08	0.37	0.05	1	0.82	1.09	0.53	2.25	
Often or always lonely (Ref. category)										

	Excellent self-rated health	-0.63	0.39	2.57	1	0.11	0.53	0.25	1.15
	Very good self-rated health	-0.45	0.36	1.54	1	0.22	0.64	0.31	1.30
	Good self-rated health	-0.09	0.35	0.06	1	0.80	0.92	0.46	1.82
	Fair self-rated health	-0.23	0.36	0.41	1	0.52	0.80	0.39	1.61
	Poor self-rated health (Ref. category)								
	No partner in the household	-0.18	0.15	1.41	1	0.24	0.84	0.62	1.12
	Having a partner in the household (Ref. category)								
Involuntary exit	Intercept	2.23	1.50	2.21	1	0.14			
	Age	0.00	0.02	0.00	1	0.95	1.00	0.95	1.05
	Years of education	-0.11	0.02	20.95	1	<.001	0.90	0.86	0.94
	Not helping others the day before	-0.33	0.20	2.80	1	0.09	0.72	0.49	1.06
	Less than 30 minutes helping others the day before	-1.24	0.44	8.02	1	0.01	0.29	0.12	0.68
	Between 30 and 60 minutes helping others the day before	-0.20	0.28	0.51	1	0.48	0.82	0.48	1.41
	More than 60 minutes helping others the day before (Ref. category)								
	Not lonely	-0.41	0.39	1.12	1	0.29	0.66	0.31	1.42
	Sometimes lonely	0.11	0.41	0.07	1	0.79	1.12	0.50	2.48
	Often or always lonely (Ref. category)								
	Excellent self-rated health	-3.44	0.49	48.93	1	<.001	0.03	0.01	0.08
	Very good self-rated health	-3.14	0.34	85.95	1	<.001	0.04	0.02	0.08
	Good self-rated health	-3.11	0.30	109.41	1	<.001	0.05	0.03	0.08
	Fair self-rated health	-1.80	0.29	39.58	1	<.001	0.17	0.10	0.29
	Poor self-rated health (Ref. category)								
	No partner in the household	0.01	0.23	0.00	1	0.97	1.01	0.65	1.58
	Having a partner in the household (Ref. category)								

Table A4 Nominal regression of labour market exit on age, education, helping others, loneliness, self-rated health, for women (Wave 9).

		<B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% CI for Exp(B)	
								Lower	Upper
Voluntary exit	Intercept	14.76	0.90	270.49	1	<.001			
	Age in 2020	0.24	0.01	346.21	1	<.001	1.27	1.24	1.31
	Years of education	-0.07	0.01	27.83	1	<.001	0.94	0.92	0.96
	Not helping others the day before	-0.39	0.10	14.16	1	<.001	0.68	0.55	0.83
	Less than 30 minutes helping others the day before	-0.91	0.24	14.97	1	<.001	0.40	0.25	0.64
	Between 30 and 60 minutes helping others the day before	-0.56	0.18	9.44	1	0.00	0.57	0.40	0.82
	More than 60 minutes helping others the day before (Ref. category)								
	Not lonely	-0.26	0.25	1.12	1	0.29	0.77	0.47	1.25
	Sometimes lonely	0.20	0.26	0.62	1	0.43	1.23	0.74	2.04
	Often or always lonely (Ref. category)								
	Excellent self-rated health	0.46	0.40	1.32	1	0.25	1.58	0.72	3.45
	Very good self-rated health	0.42	0.38	1.21	1	0.27	1.52	0.72	3.19
	Good self-rated health	0.70	0.37	3.58	1	0.06	2.02	0.98	4.18
	Fair self-rated health	0.47	0.38	1.53	1	0.22	1.60	0.76	3.36
	Poor self-rated health (Ref. category)								
	No partner in the household	-0.39	0.11	12.11	1	<.001	0.68	0.54	0.84
Having a partner in the household (Ref. category)									
Involuntary exit	Intercept	-4.07	1.28	10.13	1	0.00			
	Age in 2020	0.08	0.02	16.48	1	<.001	1.09	1.04	1.13
	Years of education	-0.06	0.02	7.10	1	0.01	0.95	0.91	0.99
	Not helping others the day before	-0.49	0.16	9.38	1	0.00	0.61	0.45	0.84
	Less than 30 minutes helping others the day before	-0.92	0.39	5.60	1	0.02	0.40	0.19	0.85
	Between 30 and 60 minutes helping others the day before	-1.12	0.35	10.12	1	0.00	0.33	0.17	0.65

More than 60 minutes helping others the day before (Ref. category)								
Not lonely	-0.51	0.31	2.70	1	0.10	0.60	0.33	1.10
Sometimes lonely	-0.18	0.33	0.29	1	0.59	0.84	0.44	1.61
Often or always lonely (Ref. category)								
Excellent self-rated health	-2.17	0.42	26.53	1	<.001	0.11	0.05	0.26
Very good self-rated health	-2.42	0.35	48.15	1	<.001	0.09	0.05	0.18
Good self-rated health	-1.73	0.29	35.29	1	<.001	0.18	0.10	0.31
Fair self-rated health	-0.86	0.29	8.62	1	0.00	0.43	0.24	0.75
Poor self-rated health (Ref. category)								
No partner in the household	-0.12	0.18	0.48	1	0.49	0.89	0.63	1.25
Having a partner in the household (Ref. category)								

Table A5 Regression results of multilevel models. Outcome 2: 0 if the individual has spent 12 months in employment, unemployment, education, retirement (not-at-risk), and 1 otherwise (at-risk).

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
VARIABLES	Base	Base with controls	Base without care	With contextual	2019	2022
Female		0.002*** (0.000)	0.132*** (0.001)	0.007*** (0.001)	0.003** (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)
Couple		-0.026*** (0.000)	0.023*** (0.001)	-0.026*** (0.001)	-0.034*** (0.002)	-0.029*** (0.002)
Rural		0.005*** (0.000)	0.005*** (0.000)	0.005*** (0.000)	0.005*** (0.001)	0.008*** (0.001)
Limitation		0.127*** (0.000)	0.121*** (0.001)	0.133*** (0.000)	0.135*** (0.002)	0.127*** (0.002)
Primary education		-0.065*** (0.002)	-0.086*** (0.002)	-0.071*** (0.002)	-0.078*** (0.006)	-0.092*** (0.007)
Lower secondary		-0.077*** (0.002)	-0.137*** (0.002)	-0.090*** (0.002)	-0.097*** (0.006)	-0.102*** (0.006)
Upper secondary		-0.094*** (0.002)	-0.187*** (0.002)	-0.108*** (0.002)	-0.116*** (0.006)	-0.124*** (0.006)
Post-secondary non tertiary		-0.108*** (0.002)	-0.227*** (0.003)	-0.121*** (0.002)	-0.126*** (0.007)	-0.137*** (0.007)
Tertiary education		-0.121*** (0.002)	-0.253*** (0.002)	-0.136*** (0.002)	-0.140*** (0.006)	-0.141*** (0.006)
Wealth taxes, Second 20%		-0.016*** (0.001)	-0.017*** (0.001)	-0.014*** (0.001)	-0.005* (0.003)	-0.013*** (0.003)
Wealth taxes, Middle 20%		-0.018*** (0.001)	-0.021*** (0.001)	-0.018*** (0.001)	-0.010*** (0.003)	-0.015*** (0.002)
Wealth taxes, Fourth 20%		-0.019*** (0.001)	-0.022*** (0.001)	-0.019*** (0.001)	-0.009*** (0.003)	-0.019*** (0.002)
Wealth taxes, Highest 20%		-0.017*** (0.001)	-0.018*** (0.001)	-0.018*** (0.001)	-0.007*** (0.002)	-0.020*** (0.002)
If spent at least 6 months in domestic tasks and care responsibilities		0.917*** (0.001)		0.917*** (0.001)	0.927*** (0.003)	0.916*** (0.003)
GDP per capita				-0.073*** (0.004)	0.006 (0.014)	-0.003 (0.012)
Employment incentives				-0.014*** (0.002)	-0.016 (0.053)	-0.124*** (0.047)
Formal age of retirement				0.005*** (0.000)	0.005*** (0.001)	0.005*** (0.001)

Constant	0.139*** (0.006)	0.159*** (0.004)	0.205*** (0.006)	0.601*** (0.041)	-0.243 (0.153)	-0.103 (0.138)
Observations	2,113,262	1,687,883	1,690,550	1,300,512	123,572	107,057
Number of groups	116	111	111	98	98	70
Level 2	Region	Region	Region	Region	Region	Region
Number of obs	2.113e+06	1.688e+06	1.691e+06	1.301e+06	123572	107057

Note: Comma (,) used as number separator, while a period is used a decimal separator.

Source: Authors' elaboration based on EU-SILC data and data from the ECDC

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Consortium members

OSLOMET

OSLO METROPOLITAN UNIVERSITY
STORBYUNIVERSITETET

arco

Contact

Elisabeth Ugreninov, OsloMet, Norway
eugren@oslomet.no